

Complexes of Some Bivalent Metal Ions with Furan-2-Thiohydrazide

B. N. KESHARI and L. K. MISHRA*

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005

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Complexes of some bivalent metal ions with furan-2-thiohydrazide (fthH) of the general formulae $[M(fth)_n] \cdot nH_2O$ ($M = Ni^{2+}, Cu^{2+}, Zn^{2+}, Cd^{2+}, Pb^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+} and $n = 0$ or 1), $[Ni(fth)_2]X_2$ ($X = Cl^-$ and $\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}$), $[Cu(fth)X_2]$ ($X = Cl^-$ or Br^-), $[M(fth)Cl_2]$ ($M = Cd^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+}) and $[Cd(fth)_2Br_2]$ have been prepared and characterised by analytical, uv and ir spectral, electrical conductance and magnetic susceptibility data.

FURAN-2-thiohydrazide (fthH) is a potent nitrogen and sulphur donor ligand and it can coordinate to metal ions in thione or thiol form (Fig. 1) as neutral or monoanionic ligand.

Fig. 1

Complexes of some acetthiohydrazides and acetthiohydrazones with Ni^{2+} , VO^{2+} and Mo^{3+} are known¹⁻⁶. Except VO^{2+} , the complexes of other metals with fthH have not been studied⁴. In the present paper we report a study on the complexes of Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} and Hg^{2+} with fthH.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared as reported by Jensen⁷. Metal salts used were either BDH AnalR grade or E. Merck extra-pure grade.

Preparation of metal complexes :

$[Ni(fth)_2]X_2$ ($X = Cl^-$ or $\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}$): An ethanolic solution of nickel(II) salt [(0.01 mole in ~50 ml ethanol) (in case of sulphate, $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ dissolved in ~5 ml of water and diluted with ~40 ml of ethanol)] was acidified with a few drops of appropriate acid (pH 2-3) and then treated with a slight excess of the ligand (0.025 mole) dissolved in absolute ethanol. The complex separated out from the resulting orange yellow solution on adding an excess of dry ether. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in *vacuo* over $CaCl_2$.

$[Cd(fth)_2Br_2]$ and $[M(fth)X_2]$ (For $M = Cd^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+} , $X = Cl^-$, and for $M = Cu^{2+}$, $X = Cl^-$ or Br^-): About 0.01 mole of metal(II) halide was dissolved in 60 ml ethanol and treated with stoichiometric proportion of ethanolic solution of the

ligand with stirring, when dihalo complexes separated out gradually. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried as above.

$[M(fth)_2] \cdot nH_2O$ ($M = Ni^{2+}, Cu^{2+}, Zn^{2+}, Cd^{2+}, Pb^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+} and $n = 0$ or 1): An aqueous ethanolic solution of hydrated metal acetate was treated with ethanolic solution of the ligand (1 : 2.5 molar ratio). The pH of the resulting solution was raised to 7-8 by adding an aqueous solution of sodium acetate when neutral *bis* chelates separated out immediately. Except Cu(II), other complexes were digested on a steam bath for ~20 min. The product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried as above.

Electrical conductivity, magnetic susceptibility, electronic absorption and reflectance spectra of the complexes were recorded as reported earlier⁸. The infrared spectra of the ligand and its complexes were recorded in the range of $4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in KBr disc or nujol mull on Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer at B. H. U., Varanasi. Prominent ir bands and their assignments are given in Table 3.

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analysis, magnetic moment values at room temperature (304-305 K) and molar electrical conductance value in DMF (31°) are given in Table 1. The reflectance or absorption band positions with their probable assignments are recorded in Table 2.

It is found that in neutral or alkaline solution ($pH > 6$), fthH forms neutral *bis* chelates $[M(fth)_2] \cdot nH_2O$ ($M = Ni^{2+}, Cd^{2+}, Zn^{2+}, Cu^{2+}, Pb^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+}) with bivalent metal ions. In acidic medium ($pH \sim 3$), it coordinates in thione form and forms *bis* chelated complex salts $[Ni(fth)_2]X_2$ ($X = Cl^-$ or $\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}$) and $[Cd(fth)_2Br_2]$ as well as dihalo complexes $[M(fth)Cl_2]$ ($M = Cd^{2+}$ or Hg^{2+}) and $[Cu(fth)X_2]$ ($X = Cl^-$ or Br^-). Cobalt(II) is readily oxidised in the presence of the ligand and no pure cobalt(II) complexes could be isolated.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL RESULTS, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND MOLAR ELECTRICAL CONDUCTANCE VALUE OF COMPLEXES AT 30°

Complex	Colour	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	%M		%N		%Halogen/sulphate		Δ_M ($\text{Ohm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$)
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
$[\text{Ni}(\text{fthH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Light yellow	Dia.	14.29	14.12	13.40	13.54	17.34	17.16	129
$[\text{Ni}(\text{fthH})_2]\text{SO}_4$	Light yellow	Dia.	13.20	13.38	12.72	12.76	21.60	21.88	—
$[\text{Ni}(\text{fth})_2]$	Light yellow	Dia.	16.90	17.13	16.29	16.34	—	—	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$	Green	1.87	23.09	22.97	9.95	10.13	25.84	25.68	16
$[\text{Cu}(\text{fthH})\text{Br}_2]$	Dark brown	1.37	17.50	17.38	7.75	7.66	43.90	43.74	12
$[\text{Cu}(\text{fth})_2]$	Dark brown	1.72	18.54	18.39	15.98	16.21	—	—	7
$[\text{Zn}(\text{fth})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light yellow	Dia.	17.75	17.88	15.27	15.32	—	—	8
$[\text{Cd}(\text{fth})_2]$	Cream	Dia.	28.37	28.50	14.30	14.20	—	—	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$	Cream	Dia.	34.38	34.53	8.59	8.60	21.30	21.84	25
$[\text{Cd}(\text{fthH})_2\text{Br}_2]$	Light pink	Dia.	24.50	24.63	12.15	12.27	34.62	35.04	28
$[\text{Pb}(\text{fth})_2]$	Light yellow	Dia.	42.18	42.36	11.34	11.45	—	—	5
$[\text{Hg}(\text{fth})_2]$	Cream yellow	Dia.	41.45	41.58	11.71	11.61	—	—	—
$[\text{Hg}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$	Cream	Dia.	48.39	48.50	7.03	6.77	17.06	17.16	—

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS

Compound	Medium	Spectral band position		Assignments
		cm^{-1}	(ϵ_{max})	
fthH (ligand)	Ethanol	37730 32260	(10634) (8940)	$n \rightarrow \pi$ $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$
$[\text{Ni}(\text{fthH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	Reflectance	19610m		$^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$
$[\text{Ni}(\text{fth})_2]$	Reflectance	25640sh 9820sh		C-T $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$	Reflectance	23810mbr 14285-12200		C-T + $^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3E_g$
$[\text{Cu}(\text{fthH})\text{Br}_2]$	Reflectance	23260mbr 16129-13890br.w		$^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3B_{2g} + ^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3A_{1g}$ $^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3E_g + C \rightarrow T$ $^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3B_{2g} + ^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3A_{1g}$

s=strong, sh=shoulder, m=medium, br=broad and w=weak.

TABLE 3—IMPORTANT IR BANDS AND THEIR ASSIGNMENTS

Compound	$\nu(\text{NH}) + \nu(\text{NH}_2)$	$\delta(\text{NH}_2)$	Thioamide bands				$\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$
			I	II	III	IV		
fth(Ligand)	3230m 3130s 3105m	1580s	1550vs	1310vs	1252s	820m	—	—
$[\text{Ni}(\text{fthH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$	3109s	1617vs	1579m	1330sh	1280sbr 1250sbr	805w	415w	370w
$[\text{Ni}(\text{fth})_2]$	3118mbr	1615vs	1578m	1341s	1280s	720m	416m	370m 305m
$[\text{Cu}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$	3140br	1610sh	1576m	1370s	1244m	820w	425w	320sh 305m
$[\text{Cu}(\text{fth})_2]$	3110m	1600m	1600m	1365s	1210m	710w	435sh	370m
$[\text{Cd}(\text{fthH})_2\text{Br}_2]$	3315s 3255m	1610s	1570m	1380w	1287m	835m	—	385w 315w
$[\text{Hg}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$	3120sbr	1610s	1570s	1375w	1280sh	810m	395w	345w
$[\text{Zn}(\text{fth})_2]$	3260m 3120m 3040m	1590s	1590s	1374s	1280m	712w	425m	385s' 312m

s=strong, w=weak, m=medium, b=broad, v=very, sh=shoulder.

The neutral bis chelates $[\text{M}(\text{fth})_2]$ are insoluble in water, ethanol, benzene etc. but dissolve appreciably in DMF. As expected, the DMF solution of the complexes are non-conducting supporting their non-ionic character. The acido complexes are slightly soluble in ethanol and methanol but dissolve fairly in DMF. The molar conductance value of the complex salt $[\text{Ni}(\text{fthH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ falls in the range of 1 : 2 electrolyte⁹ while dihalo complexes $[\text{M}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$ (M=Cu²⁺ or Cd²⁺) and

$[\text{Cd}(\text{fthH})_2\text{Br}_2]$ show negligible conductance value indicating non-ionic nature of the complexes. A small conductance value ($\Delta_M = 10-20 \text{ Ohm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) of dihalo complexes $[\text{M}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$ can be attributed to solvation in the complexes.

Excepting Cu(II), the complexes of other elements are diamagnetic (Table 1). The diamagnetism of Ni(II) complexes suggests their square planar structure. At room temperature, $[\text{Cu}(\text{fthH})$

Cl_2] is magnetically dilute¹⁰. The subnormal magnetic moment values of $[\text{Cu}(\text{fthH})\text{Br}_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{fth})_2]$ can be attributed to super-exchange interaction or partial metal-metal bonding in the complexes^{11,12}.

The electronic reflectance spectra of nickel(II) complexes are similar to the spectra of square planar nickel(II) complexes¹³. The reflectance spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{fth})_2]$ does not display distinct absorption band in visible region. Dihalo complexes $[\text{Cu}(\text{fthH})\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$ or Br^-) display two to three bands in the visible region. The broad asymmetric band in the region 14300-11700 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the combination of ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$ transitions while the second band near 23800-20400 cm^{-1} is attributed to ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ transition similar to distorted octahedral copper(II) complexes^{14,15}.

IR spectra : In 3μ region, the ligand displays a number of bands attributable to $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu_s(\text{NH}_2)$ and $\nu_{as}(\text{NH}_2)$ vibrations¹⁶. In inner *bis*-chelates, these bands are shifted to lower frequencies and merge together to give a broad band indicative of involvement of NH_2 nitrogen in bond formation. The ir spectrum of the *bis*-chelate $[\text{Cd}(\text{fthH})_2\text{Br}_2]$ displays sharp NH_2 stretches while the complexes $[\text{Ni}(\text{fthH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{M}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Cd}^{2+}$, Cu^{2+} or Hg^{2+}) display only one broad and medium band 3080-3120 cm^{-1} . Thus, it is inferred that excepting $[\text{Cd}(\text{fthH})_2\text{Br}_2]$, NH_2 is involved in coordination in all the complexes¹⁷.

The ligand displays NH_2 deformation vibration at 1580 cm^{-1} . In the complexes, the band is raised to higher frequencies by 20-40 cm^{-1} supporting the involvement of NH_2 group in bonding¹⁷. The ligand displays a number of bands in the region 1550-750 cm^{-1} , attributable to furan ring $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$, $\delta(\text{C}-\text{H})$ and thiohydrazide group thioamide bands^{17,18}, $\beta(\text{NH}_2)$, $\nu(\text{N}-\text{N})$ and $\rho_w(\text{NH}_2)$ vibrations. The thioamide bands (I to IV) of free ligand are located at 1550, 1310, 1252 and 820 cm^{-1} and these are affected appreciably in its metal complexes. In neutral *bis*-chelates, the thioamide band IV, mainly due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibration, is shifted to lower frequencies and observed near 715 ± 5 cm^{-1} while in the complex salts $[\text{Ni}(\text{fthH})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{M}(\text{fthH})\text{Cl}_2]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Cd}^{2+}$, Cu^{2+} or Hg^{2+}), the band is shifted to lower frequencies only by 10-15 cm^{-1} . An appreciable lowering of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ vibration in neutral *bis*-chelates indicates the coordination of the thiol sulphur by deprotonation of the $-\text{SH}$ group¹⁹. The thioamide bands I to II are shifted

to higher frequencies by 20-40 cm^{-1} and observed with reduced intensity in almost all the complexes¹⁹. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ band of furan ring is observed at 1020 cm^{-1} and is not affected appreciably in its complexes indicating that furan ring oxygen is not involved in coordination.

In far-infrared region, the free ligand displays a number of medium to strong bands at 648, 595, 562, 445 and 388 cm^{-1} attributable to ring deformation, $\delta(\text{HNCS})$, $\delta(\text{C}-\text{N})$ and $\delta(\text{N}-\text{N})$ vibrations. In complexes, these bands are slightly shifted in position and observed with reduced intensity mostly at lower wave number. The new bands in complexes located in the range of 440-305 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to $\text{M}-\text{N}$ and $\text{M}-\text{S}$ stretching vibrations¹⁹⁻²¹.

References

1. K. A. JENSEN and J. F. MIQUEL, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 6, 189.
2. E. LARSEN, P. TRINDERUP, B. OLSEN and K. J. WATSON, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1970, 24, 261.
3. J. GABEL, E. LARSEN and P. TRINDERUP, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1977, 31A, 657.
4. (Mrs.) U. KUMARI, C. P. SINGH and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 255.
5. B. N. KESHARI and L. K. MISHRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, 20A, 883.
6. J. R. DILWORTH, J. H. P. VELLA, K. VENKATASUBRAMAMAN and JON A. ZUBRETA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, 18, 268.
7. K. A. JENSEN and C. PEDERSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1961, 15, 1097.
8. S. P. GHOSH and L. K. MISHRA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, 7, 515.
9. J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. FUJITA, D. J. PHILLIPS, J. A. WALMSLEY and S. Y. TYREE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 3770.
10. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1976, p. 916.
11. E. A. BOUDREAU, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 506.
12. C. M. HARRIS, B. F. HOSKINS and R. L. MARTIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3728.
13. S. I. SHUPAK, E. BILLING, R. J. CLARK, R. WILLIAMS and H. B. GRAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 86, 4594.
14. W. MANCH and W. C. FERNELIUS, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1961, 38, 192.
15. A. D. HARRIA, H. B. JONASSEN and R. D. ARCHER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 147.
16. J. V. QUAGLIANO, G. V. SVATOS and B. C. CURRAN, *Anal. Chem.*, 1954, 26, 429.
17. O. N. R. RAO, R. VENKATARAGHAVAN and T. R. KASTURI, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1964, 82, 86.
18. G. R. BURNS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 277.
19. (Miss) LAKSHMI, B. SINGH and U. AGARWALA, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 2341.
20. M. AKBAR ALI, S. E. LIVINGSTONE and D. J. PHILLIPS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, 5, 119, 493.
21. D. M. ADAMS and J. B. CORNELL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968A, 1299.